

Rice seed samples in glass ampules. Hunan, China, 1987.

2. Ease in operating. It is very easy to seal the ampule vials using a bunsen burner and a pair of tweezers.
3. Ease in keeping. The ampule is made of glass, which cannot be affected by moisture, insects, and rats. It can be stored in normal conditions.
4. Low cost. The ampules are very cheap. One 2-ml ampule can store 20-30 rice seeds, enough to use for breeding parents. A 20-ml ampule bottle can hold 500 rice seeds.
5. Use for other crops. Glass ampules can be used for other small-seed crops, such as wheat, vegetables, and rapeseeds. □

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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Response of new rice varieties to N

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Rice variety PR106 covers about 80% of the area under rice in Punjab. Recently, yield at experimental farms and in farmers' fields have dropped markedly. Susceptibility of cultivars to a number of plant diseases was found to be the major reason. Two new varieties with high yield potential — PR108 and PR109 — are more resistant to plant pathogens. Because Punjab soils are inherently deficient in organic matter N, a substantial response of the three varieties to applied N is expected.

We studied the response of the three varieties to four N levels during 1986 summer. Treatments were laid out in a split-plot design with three replications. Soils (pH 8.4 EC 0.16 dS/m, 0.30%

Grain yield, N uptake, and yield parameters of 3 rice varieties at different levels of N application, Punjab, India, 1986 summer.

Variety	No N	90 kg N/ha	120 kg N/ha	150 kg N/ha	Mean
<i>Grain yield (t/ha)</i>					
PR106	2.7	5.5	5.8	6.2	5.0
PR108	3.3	6.0	6.3	6.7	5.6
PR109	3.1	5.7	6.1	6.4	5.3
Mean	3.0	5.7	6.1	6.4	
LSD (P=0.05): N levels = 0.27, varieties = 0.31, NXV = ns					
<i>Effective tillers/plant</i>					
PR106	8.4	9.4	9.7	10.7	9.6
PR108	8.5	9.5	11.5	11.9	10.4
PR109	8.7	9.1	10.6	11.5	10.0
Mean	8.5	9.3	10.6	11.4	
LSD (P=0.05): N levels = 0.5, varieties = 0.4, NXV = ns					
<i>Filled spikelets/panicle</i>					
PR106	92	97	99	112	100
PR108	109	115	122	127	118
PR109	94	107	109	117	107
Mean	98	106	110	119	
LSD (P=0.05): N levels = 7, varieties = 8, NXV = ns					
<i>N uptake</i>					
PR106	39	106	125	138	102
PR108	61	127	140	150	120
PR109	53	113	132	142	110
Mean	51	115	132	143	
LSD (P=0.05): N levels = 9, varieties = 8, NXV = ns					

organic C, 0.04% total N) of the experimental field was loamy sand (Typic Ustochrept) with an average percolation rate of 4 mm/h.

N as urea was applied in 3 equal splits: at transplanting and 21 and 42 d

after transplanting. A basal dose of 13 kg P and 12 kg K/ha was applied at last puddling.

All the 3 varieties responded up to 150 kg N/ha. PR108 significantly outyielded PR106 at all N levels (see

table). Yield components also were highest in PR108. PR108 matures 6-8 d earlier than PR106, an advantage for early sowing of wheat in a rice - wheat cropping system. □

Performance of overage seedlings at different N levels

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We studied the effect of N level on grain yield and yield parameters using overage seedlings of four transplanted rice varieties - Mahsuri, Sarjoo 52, Ratna, and Saket 4 in a randomized block design with four replications.

Experimental plot soil was sandy loam with pH 7.5, EC (1:2) 0.09 mmho/cm, 0.42% organic C, 17.5 kg available P/ha, and 135 kg available K/ha. Fifty-five-day-old seedlings were transplanted 10 Aug 1983 at 2-3 seedlings/hill at 20 × 10-cm spacing. Urea was applied at 0, 50, and 100 kg N/ha. Single superphosphate and muriate of potash at 18 and 32 kg/ha were basally applied.

Each increment of N significantly increased panicle number, panicle

Yield and yield attributes of overage seedlings of 4 varieties as influenced by N level. Masodha, India.

Treatment	Panicles/m ²	Panicle weight (g)	1000-grain weight (g)	Plant height (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)
N level (kg/ha)					
0	35	1.6	20.3	73	1.5
50	44	1.7	20.9	82	2.4
100	52	2.0	21.7	90	2.9
CD (0.05)	7.0	0.2	0.3	3	0.1
Variety					
Mahsuri	42	1.7	15.2	94	2.6
Sarjoo 52	35	2.3	27.1	77	2.3
Ratna	41	1.7	21.6	79	2.1
Saket 4	54	1.3	20.1	77	1.9
CD (0.05)	4	0.3	0.4	3	0.1

weight, test weight, plant height, and grain yield (see table), but average N use efficiency was low, 17.7 kg grain/kg N with 50 kg N/ha and 14.1 kg grain/kg N with 100 kg N/ha. In general, grain yield and yield parameters were adversely affected by planting overage seedlings, which resulted in low grain yields for all varieties. Long-duration Mahsuri performed better than medium

Sarjoo 52 and short Ratna and Saket 4. Although Sarjoo 52 yields higher than other varieties under normal conditions, Mahsuri performed better under these conditions, probably because its longer duration gave sufficient growth and development time to overcome late seedling planting. N application was beneficial to grain yield, even with overage seedlings. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

GRAIN QUALITY

Two promising scented rice varieties for the Mekong Delta

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Two promising scented rice varieties — Nang-thom sel. and Nang-huong-ran sel. — have been released for specific areas in the Mekong Delta. The varieties are suitable for the early Jul - late Dec crop in various waterlogged ricefields.

Nang-huong-ran sel. is distinguished

Table 1. Agricultural characteristics and grain quality of promising scented varieties. Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam.

Character	Nang-thom sel.	Nang-huong-ran sel.
Culm length (cm)	141.8	145.6
Growth duration (d)	160.3	165.3
Panicles/plant	10.6	7.3
Panicle length (cm)	23.7	23.6
Fully filled spikelets/panicle	108.0	131.3
1000-grain wt (g)	23.4	24.9
Grain yield (t/ha)	3.85	4.88
Culm strength ^b	5-7	1-3
Brown rice length (mm)	7.03	6.62
Brown rice length-to-width ratio	3.36	3.22
Chakiness ^b	1	1
Scent ^b	2	1

^aAv of 4-yr trials. ^bStandard evaluation system for rice codes.